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STUDY OF TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCE OF ELECTROPHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF $\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Pr}_x\text{Te}$ CRYSTALS

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Summary. *The results of the study of the electrophysical properties of $\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Pr}_x\text{Te}$ crystals in a wide temperature range are presented. The temperature dependences of the electrical conductivity, Hall and thermoelectric coefficients of these crystals were studied, and based on the experimental results, the fundamental semiconductor parameters of these crystals: the width of the forbidden zones, the type of conductivity, the concentration and mobility of free charge carriers were determined in the temperature range of 100-375 K.*

Key words: *Hall coefficient, thermopower, conductivity type, electrical conductivity, band gap width, charge carrier*

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ТЕМПЕРАТУРНОЙ ЗАВИСИМОСТИ ЭЛЕКТРОФИЗИЧЕСКИХ СВОЙСТВ КРИСТАЛЛОВ $\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Pr}_x\text{Te}$

Аннотация. *Представлены результаты исследования электрофизических свойств кристаллов $\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Pr}_x\text{Te}$ в широком диапазоне температур. Изучены температурные зависимости электропроводности, коэффициентов Холла и термоЭДС этих кристаллов и на основании экспериментальных результатов определены фундаментальные полупроводниковые параметры этих кристаллов: ширина запрещенных зон, тип проводимости, концентрация и подвижность свободных носителей заряда в диапазоне температур 100-375 К.*

Ключевые слова: *коэффициент Холла, термоЭДС, тип проводимости, электропроводность, ширина запрещенных зон, носитель заряда*

INTRODUCTION

In [1], by constructing the phase diagram of the SnTe-PrTe system using differential thermal, X-ray phase, and microstructural analyses, it was determined that in this system, solubility is observed in the range of 0–4 mol% PrTe [2,3]. There was no information available regarding the study of the electrophysical properties of the crystals detected within the specified range. In this article, the electrophysical properties of the solid solutions obtained in the $\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Pr}_x\text{Te}$ system have been investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL PART

The study of the electrophysical properties was carried out using the method described in [4].

Figures 2 and 3 present the results of experimental investigations of the temperature dependence of the specific electrical conductivity and Hall coefficients of $\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Pr}_x\text{Te}$ solid solutions in the temperature range of 100–900 K.

As seen in Figure 2, when the temperature changes within the interval of 80–250 K, the specific electrical conductivity of the studied crystals decreases. Starting from this temperature, as the temperature increases up to 500 K, the electrical conductivity of all the examined samples sharply decreases. Beginning from 500 K, due to the onset of intrinsic conductivity, the conductivity increases. This is because the intrinsic electrons in the valence band, by absorbing energy equal to or greater than the width of the forbidden band, transition into the conduction band. $\lg \sigma = f\left(\frac{10^3}{T}\right)$ based

on the high-temperature trend of the dependencies, it was determined that the width of the forbidden band decreases as Sn atoms in the SnTe lattice are substituted by Pr atoms and the amount of Pr increases. When the content of Pr reaches 4 mol%, the width of the forbidden band is 0.15 eV, i.e., it has decreased by 0.05 eV.

This is due to the fact that in the SnTe lattice, Pr atoms with an ionic radius of 1 Å replace Sn atoms with an ionic radius of 0.67 Å. It should be noted that the width of the forbidden band determined based on the temperature dependence of the electrical conductivity corresponds to $T=0$ K, i.e., in reality, the width of the forbidden band itself depends on the temperature. This dependence is expressed as

$$\Delta E(T) = \Delta E_0(T=0) + \beta T$$

Naturally, the value of the forbidden band width determined based on the electrical conductivity agrees well with the value determined based on optical measurements.

It should be noted that the decrease in electrical conductivity at low temperatures is a result of the decrease in the concentration of impurities in that temperature range. The sharp decrease in σ in the temperature range of 300-500 K is a result of the fact that the concentration of charge carriers remains constant and the mobility is mainly due to scattering from thermal oscillations of the lattices. With a further increase in temperature, the transition of eigenelectrons from the valence band to the conduction band occurs. Since this transition occurs according to an exponential law, the transition from additive conductivity to intrinsic conductivity occurs in a very narrow interval.

Figure 3 shows the temperature dependences of the Hall coefficients of $\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Pr}_x\text{Te}$ crystals. The studies were conducted in the temperature range of 80-900 K. As can be seen from Figure 3, the Hall coefficient increases anomalously when the temperature increases from 80 K to 250 K. In the temperature range of 250-400 K, the Hall coefficients of the studied crystals remain constant, and after ≈ 400 K they decrease with the onset of peculiar conductivity. This type of dependence was also found in the base compound SnTe and its structural analogues, and the reason for this is associated with the fact that these compounds have complex zone structures.

As can be seen from Figures 2 and 3, the nature of the change in the temperature dependence of the electrical conductivity and Hall coefficient is the same for all the crystals studied. That is, as the amount of Pr in the composition of $\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Pr}_x\text{Te}$ solid solutions increases, the Hall coefficient decreases and the specific electrical conductivity increases. It should be noted that the values of the width of the forbidden zone determined based on the Hall coefficient and the values determined based on the electrical conductivity agree well with each other.

The temperature dependences of the thermo-e.m.f. coefficients of $\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Pr}_x\text{Te}$ crystals were also measured in the temperature range of 80-900 K. The results are given in Figure 4. As can be seen, at low temperatures, i.e. in the temperature range of 80-400 K, the thermo-e.m.f. coefficient increases, and after 450 K it decreases due to the onset of specific conductivity. Analogous dependences were observed in SnTe and GeTe compounds, as well as in other semiconductors with a complex band structure. Let us consider that the nature of $\sigma(T)$, $R(T)$ and $\alpha(T)$ dependences was the same in all the studied solid solutions. This is due to the fact that both the base compound SnTe and the solid solutions based on it $\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Pr}_x\text{Te}$ crystallize in the same cubic syngony.

The temperature dependences of the Hall conductivities of $\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Pr}_x\text{Te}$ solid solutions are given in Figure 5. As can be seen from this figure, the conductivities are relatively weak at low temperatures, and decrease sharply at high temperatures. This is due to the fact that at low temperatures, the scattering of charge carriers from defects and impurity ions predominates, while at high temperatures, their scattering from longitudinal acoustic phonons predominates.

It can additionally be noted that although attempts have been made to explain the complexities observed in the temperature dependence of the kinetic parameters of the SnTe compound based on its band structure, a fully accurate explanation has not yet been achieved. Since such explanations are associated with the presence of resonance states in structural analogs of SnTe, such as PbTe and GeTe compounds, it can be reasoned that dopants and selective defects in SnTe and its solid solutions also

give rise to resonance levels. As their contribution to scattering is of a selective nature, this manifests itself in the variation of kinetic parameters. Figure 4 shows the thermo-e.m.f. coefficients of $\text{Sn}_{0.95}\text{Pr}_{0.05}\text{Te}$ and $\text{Sn}_{0.96}\text{Pr}_{0.04}\text{Te}$ solid solutions, and Figure 5 shows the temperature dependences of the Hall conductivities. As can be seen from Figure 4, the thermo-e.m.f. of these crystals coefficients increase from 85 $\mu\text{V}/\text{degree}$ to 150 $\mu\text{V}/\text{degree}$ when the temperature changes from 300 to 400K. However, starting from 400 K, a decrease in the thermo-e.m.f. coefficient is observed for both compositions. The temperature dependence of the Hall mobility for these crystals is given in Figure 5. As seen from these dependencies, the $\mu(T)$ behavior follows a typical pattern for doped semiconductors. That is, as the temperature increases from 100 K to 200 K, a slight decrease in mobility is observed due to the scattering of charge carriers by ionized impurities. At higher temperatures, starting around 300 K, a sharper decrease in mobility occurs as a result of scattering from the thermal vibrations of atoms. At room temperature, the average mobility is approximately $\mu \approx 200 \text{ cm}^2/\text{V}\cdot\text{s}$. An analysis of the temperature dependencies of the electrical conductivity (σ), Hall coefficient (R), and thermo-e.m.f. (α) shows that for all the studied crystals, within the doped conduction region, an increase in temperature leads to a decrease in σ . As intrinsic conduction begins — that is, when electrons from the valence band transition to the conduction band — an increase in σ is observed. In these crystals, anomalies typical for materials with complex band structures are observed in the temperature dependencies of the Hall coefficient and, to some extent, the thermo-e.m.f. coefficient — particularly an increase in both R and α .

This increase can be explained based on the assumption that the studied crystals possess a complex band structure, namely, that the valence band is composed of two additional sub-bands formed by heavy and light holes.

In the presence of heavy holes, the Hall coefficient [5,6] is given by:

$$R = \frac{A}{ec_0} \cdot \frac{p_1\mu_1^2 + p_2\mu_2^2}{(p_1\mu_1 + p_2\mu_2)^2} = R_0 \frac{(1 + p_2/p_1)[1 + (p_2/p_1)b']^2}{[1 + (p_2/p_1)b']^2} \quad (1)$$

$$b' = \mu_2 / \mu_1$$

Here, $R_0 = \frac{A}{pec_0}$ is the Hall coefficient at low temperatures, $p = p_1 + p_2$ where p_1 and p_2 are the concentrations of heavy and light holes, respectively.

It should be noted that R_{\max}/R_0 depends only on the ratio of mobilities in the subbands and is independent of their energy difference. If $b' = \frac{\mu_2}{\mu_1}$ depends weakly on temperature, then the Hall coefficient primarily depends on the distribution of charge carriers between the subbands that constitute the valence band.

If the mobility of the holes in the second band is much smaller, i.e., $\mu_2 < \mu_1 \ll 1$, their contribution to the Hall effect becomes negligible. Due to the transfer of holes into the second band, the concentration of free charge carriers

$$R = \frac{A}{ecp_2} \quad (2)$$

decreases, and consequently, the Hall coefficient increases sharply. Since the Hall coefficient reaches its maximum when $p_1 = p_2$, we obtain:

$$R_{\max} = R_0 \frac{4b'^2}{(1 + b')^2} \quad (3)$$

This relation can be easily derived based on the two-band model.

The fact that the studied materials have a complex band structure is also reflected in the investigation of their thermo-e.m.f. coefficient. For example, in $\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Pr}_x\text{Te}$ crystals, an initial increase followed by a decrease in the thermo-e.m.f. coefficient is observed with increasing temperature. This behavior can be explained as follows. According to the two-band model, the thermo-e.m.f. coefficient

is defined as [7,8]:

$$\alpha = \frac{\alpha_{p_1} \cdot b' \cdot p_1 + \alpha_{p_2}}{b'p_1 + p_2} \quad (4)$$

where α_{p_1} and α_{p_2} are the thermo-e.m.f. coefficients corresponding to the light and heavy hole bands, respectively. If the electrical conductivity of the heavy holes is smaller than that of the light holes, the term p_2 in the denominator of expression (4) can be neglected. Furthermore, if $\alpha_{p_1} \cdot p_2 \ll \alpha_{p_1} \cdot p_1 \cdot b'$, then the total thermo-e.m.f. coefficient becomes approximately equal to that of the light hole band: $\alpha \approx \alpha_{p_1}$

For a simple parabolic band structure, the thermo-e.m.f. coefficient is given by:

$$\alpha = \frac{k}{e} \left[\frac{(r+2)F_{r+2}(\eta^*)}{(r+1)F_r(\eta^*)} - \eta^* \right] \quad (5)$$

Here, $F_r(\eta^*)$ and $F_{r+2}(\eta^*)$ are the Fermi integrals [9].

$$F_r(\eta^*) = \int_0^\infty \frac{x^r dx}{e^{x-\eta^*} + 1}$$

For a non-degenerate electron gas, equation (5) simplifies to:

$$\alpha = \frac{k}{e} \left[r + 2 + \ln \frac{2(2\pi mkT)^{3/2}}{h^3 n} \right] \quad (6)$$

Where $m = N^{2/3}(m_1 \cdot m_2 \cdot m_3)^{1/3}$ is the effective mass of the density of states, N is the number of ellipsoids, and m_1, m_2, m_3 are the principal components of the effective mass tensor.

Equation (5) is a function of the Fermi energy, and increases until the Fermi level reaches the top of the heavy hole band. Beyond this point, it remains constant, resulting in the stabilization of the thermo-e.m.f. coefficient.

If $\alpha_{p_2} \cdot p_2, \alpha_{p_1} \cdot p_1 \cdot b'$ becomes comparable in magnitude to $p_2 \ll p_1 \cdot b'$, then:

$$\alpha = \alpha_{p_1} \left(1 + \frac{\alpha_{p_1} \cdot p_2}{\alpha_{p_1} p_1 b'} \right) \quad (7)$$

Since the mobility of heavy holes is much smaller, this value is greater than α_{p_1} . As the second term increases with increasing p_2 , the total thermo-e.m.f. coefficient also increases. However, as the concentration of heavy holes continues to increase, the thermo-e.m.f. coefficient begins to decrease.

As observed from the temperature dependence of mobility, in the doped conductivity region, the mobility μ increases up to around 250 K due to scattering by ionized impurities. At higher temperatures, it decreases as a result of scattering from lattice thermal vibrations. Overall, the temperature dependencies of σ, R, α and μ confirm and support each other.

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Figure 1. Phase diagram of the SnTe–PrTe system

Figure 2. Temperature dependence of the specific electrical conductivity of $\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Pr}_x\text{Te}$ solid solutions

- 1 – $x = 0.01$;
- 2 – $x = 0.02$;
- 3 – $x = 0.03$;
- 4 – $x = 0.04$

Figure 3. Temperature dependence of the Hall coefficient of $\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Pr}_x\text{Te}$ solid solutions

- 1 – $x=0.01$;
- 2 – $x=0.02$;
- 3 – $x=0.03$;
- 4 – $x=0.04$

Figure 4. Temperature dependence of the thermo-e.m.f. coefficient of $\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Pr}_x\text{Te}$ solid solutions

- 1- $x=0.01$;
- 2- $x=0.02$;
- 3- $x=0.03$;
- 4- $x=0.04$

Figure 5. Temperature dependence of the Hall conductivity of $\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Pr}_x\text{Te}$ solid solutions

- 1- $x=0.01$;
- 2- $x=0.02$;
- 3- $x=0.03$;
- 4- $x=0.04$